

Studies on the Reduction of Potassium Permanganate by Oxalic Acid and its Homologues

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Reduction of potassium permanganate by oxalic, malonic, and succinic acids has been studied and the rate constants have been determined. The reaction is found to be autocatalytic and is mainly governed by the dissociation constants of these acids. The dissociation constants of oxalic acid ($K_1=3.8 \times 10^{-2}$, $K_2=4.9 \times 10^{-5}$), malonic acid ($K_1=1.61 \times 10^{-3}$, $K_2=2.1 \times 10^{-6}$), and succinic acid ($K_1=6.63 \times 10^{-3}$, $K_2=2.8 \times 10^{-6}$) indicate the reduction taking place by such carboxylic acids, dissociation constants of which range between 10^{-2} and 10^{-6} . In the case of succinic acid, the reducing power is very low. A mechanism of these reactions has been suggested.

The reaction between potassium permanganate and oxalic acid or an oxalate has been studied by a number of workers. According to Škrabal¹ manganic ion is an intermediate product in this reaction due to formation of some manganic complex:

Launer² suggested that the rate of this reaction was inversely proportional to the concentration of $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ ions, but this was not confirmed. He explained the mechanism of the reaction by the intermediate formation of a complex $[\text{Mn}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]^-$, which was a very fast reaction and suggested that the order was determined by the slow reduction of manganic ion to manganous state:

He observed that the composition of the reaction mixture also affected the rate of the reaction.

Lidwell and Bell³ and Bassett and Sanderson⁴ observed that the reaction was influenced by manganous sulphate and H^+ ions accelerated the reduction of Mn^{3+} ions to Mn^{2+} . MacMahon *et al.*⁵ and Ghosh *et al.*⁶ reported that formic acid was produced as an intermediate during the reaction between potassium permanganate and oxalic acid.

Although the reduction of potassium permanganate by oxalic acid has been extensively studied, its reduction has not, however, been adequately studied by the homologues

1. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1904, 42, 1.
2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 2597.
3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1303.
4. *Ibid.*, 1936, 207.
5. *This Journal*, 1943, 20, 142, 307.
6. *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1950, 19, 174.

of oxalic acid. Since there is a considerable difference in the dissociation constants of oxalic acid and its homologues, it is deemed necessary to investigate quantitatively the kinetics of the reaction of potassium permanganate with malonic and succinic acids. The interesting observations made on these reductions have been embodied in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were of extra pure quality and the solutions were prepared in fresh double distilled water.

Standard solutions of oxalic acid, malonic acid, and succinic acid were prepared by direct weighing. A standard solution of KMnO_4 was always prepared just before the start of the reaction by filtering it through a sintered glass crucible and standardising with 0.1*N* oxalic acid solution.

All experiments were carried out in diffused light and in conical flasks of pyrex glass of 250-ml capacity. Calculated amounts of the organic acid was taken in the reaction vessel, kept in a thermostat maintained at the temperature of the experiment. The flask containing KMnO_4 solution was also kept in the thermostat. The reaction was started by dropping a calculated quantity of KMnO_4 solution from a pipette into the reaction vessel. The reaction mixture (10 ml) was pipetted out at different intervals of time and titrated iodometrically with 0.01*M* sodium thiosulphate solution to estimate the unreduced KMnO_4 . The reaction was arrested during the titration by adding a piece of ice.

The rate constants were determined by the well-known formulas for the zero, uni, and bimolecular reactions. The expression for the autocatalytic rate of reaction was derived as follows.

The velocity coefficient for the autocatalytic reaction was derived by assuming the formation of some active substance, responsible for the autocatalysis.

If the formation of the autocatalyst takes place immediately on mixing the reactants, we may assume that practically at time t_0 , the concentration of the autocatalyst is y_1 (say) and if at time t , the increase in concentration of the autocatalyst be X , then the total concentration of the autocatalyst is $(y_1 + X)$ at time t .

Now, the question is how to ascertain X , even though we may assume that y_1 is very small and a constant quantity. The only possibility of representing X quantitatively is to take it to be proportional to the degree of reduction of KMnO_4 . Thus, if a is the initial concentration of KMnO_4 in the reaction mixture and x is the amount of KMnO_4 reduced at time t , then the degree of reduction is x/a , which should be proportional to X .

Now, we can frame the equation as:

$$\begin{aligned} dX/dt &= k_1 (y_1 + X) (1 - X) \\ &= k_1 y_1 (1 + X/y_1) (1 - X) \end{aligned}$$

or

$$dX/dt = K (1 + bX) (1 - X)$$

where

$$K = k_1 y_1$$

$$b = 1/y_1$$

By integrating the above equation and applying the limiting conditions to calculate the integrative constant, we get the following expression for the velocity coefficient after simplification:

$$K = 1/t(1 + b) \cdot \log (1 + bX)/(1 - X)$$

where X is the degree of reduction.

Since the autocatalytic curve is S-shaped, it must have a point of inflection where either d^2X/dt^2 or $d^2t/dX^2 = 0$ according as the point of inflection is taken along the t -axis or the X -axis.

This mathematical criterion for the point of inflection is applied to calculate the value of the constant 'b'. Thus, by equating $d^2t/dX^2 = 0$ and simplifying, we get

$$b = 1 - \frac{1}{2X}$$

In this way it is possible to calculate the values of K for the autocatalytic reaction by means of our equation.

TABLE I

$(\text{COOH})_n = 0.05M$. $\text{KMnO}_4 = 0.002M$. Temp. = 20° .

Time (t).	a-x.	x.	k_0 .	k_1 .	k_2 .	k_{auto} .
0 min.	10.0 ml	..	..	..	..	..
10	10.0	0.0 ml	..	..	..	..
20	9.5	0.5	0.05	0.00257	0.00026	0.0001085
30	7.8	2.2	0.17	0.00828	0.00094	0.003014
35	6.2	3.8	0.32	0.01305	0.00175	0.003428
40	4.2	5.8	0.40	0.02169	0.00347	0.002682
45	2.5	7.5	0.34	0.03082	0.00666	0.002891
50	1.9	8.1	0.12	0.03321	0.00842	0.002800
55	1.5	8.5	0.08	0.03449	0.01030	0.002735
60	1.4	8.6	0.02	0.03277	0.01023	0.002587
70	1.2	8.8	0.02	0.03030	0.00682	0.002313
80	0.9	9.1	0.03	0.03008	0.01262	0.002116
90	0.8	9.2	0.01	0.02805	0.01277	0.001994
100	0.7	9.3	0.01	0.02661	0.01328	0.001853

TABLE II

$\text{H}_2\text{C}(\text{COOH})_n = 0.06M$. $\text{KMnO}_4 = 0.002M$. Temp. = 30° .

Time (t).	a-x.	x.	k_0 .	k_1 .	k_2 .	k_{auto} .
0 min.	10.00 ml	..	..	..	..	..
10	9.95	0.05 ml	0.005	0.00050	0.00005	0.0002149
20	9.80	0.20	0.015	0.00101	0.00010	0.0004264
30	9.35	0.65	0.045	0.00224	0.00026	0.0009335
40	8.30	1.70	0.105	0.00465	0.00051	0.0017920
45	7.40	2.60	0.160	0.00669	0.00078	0.0022960
50	5.90	4.10	0.300	0.01055	0.00139	0.0022780
55	3.80	6.20	0.420	0.01759	0.00296	0.0020310
60	1.50	8.50	0.480	0.03162	0.00440	0.0025360
70	1.05	8.95	0.045	0.03221	0.01217	0.0028960
80	0.85	9.15	0.020	0.03080	0.01346	0.0022270

TABLE II (contd.)

Time (t).	$a-x$.	x .	k_0 .	k_1 .	k_2 .	k_{auto} .
90 min.	0.70ml	9.30ml	0.015	0.02953	0.01477	0.0020670
100	0.80	9.40	0.010	0.02813	0.01566	0.0019200
110	0.50	9.50	0.010	0.02724	0.01725	0.0018180
120	0.40	9.60	0.010	0.02679	0.02000	0.0017470
130	0.30	9.70	0.010	0.02697	0.02500	0.0017080
140	0.20	9.80	0.010	0.02796	0.03500	0.0017120

TABLE III

$$\text{H}_2\text{C}(\text{COOH})_2 = 0.05M. \quad \text{KMnO}_4 = 0.002M. \quad \text{Temp.} = 30^\circ.$$

Time (t).	$a-x$	x	k_0 .	k_1 .	k_2 .	k_{auto} .
0 min.	10.0 ml.	..	..	..	..	..
15	9.85	0.15 ml	0.010	0.00101	0.00010	0.000431
30	9.50	0.50	0.023	0.00171	0.00017	0.000723
40	8.80	1.20	0.070	0.00320	0.00340	0.001286
50	7.45	2.55	0.135	0.00588	0.00068	0.002040
55	6.15	3.85	0.260	0.00883	0.00113	0.002170
60	4.40	5.60	0.350	0.01368	0.00212	0.001772
65	2.30	7.70	0.420	0.02261	0.00515	0.002057
70	1.35	8.65	0.190	0.02861	0.00915	0.002240
80	1.00	9.00	0.035	0.02878	0.01125	0.002124
90	0.85	9.15	0.015	0.02738	0.05995	0.001853
100	0.70	9.30	0.015	0.02658	0.01328	0.001853
110	0.65	9.35	0.005	0.02485	0.01398	0.001716
120	0.55	9.45	0.010	0.02416	0.01644	0.001631
130	0.40	9.60	0.015	0.02475	0.01846	0.001613
140	0.30	9.70	0.010	0.02503	0.02310	0.001587

TABLE IV

$$\text{H}_2\text{C}(\text{COOH})_2 = 0.04M. \quad \text{KMnO}_4 = 0.002M. \quad \text{Temp.} = 30^\circ.$$

Time (t).	$a-x$.	x .	k_0 .	k_1 .	k_2 .	k_{auto} .
0 min	10.05 ml	..	..	..	..	..
15	9.95	0.10 ml	0.006	0.00073	0.00006	0.000290
30	9.65	0.40	0.020	0.00170	0.00013	0.000579
40	9.25	0.80	0.040	0.00207	0.00021	0.000964
59	8.45	1.60	0.080	0.00346	0.00037	0.001356
60	6.95	3.10	0.150	0.00614	0.00078	0.001929
65	5.70	4.35	0.250	0.00872	0.00116	0.001568
70	4.15	5.90	0.314	0.01266	0.00202	0.001552
75	2.30	7.75	0.370	0.01966	0.00447	0.001755
80	1.35	8.70	0.190	0.02509	0.00803	0.001961
90	1.10	8.95	0.025	0.02459	0.00899	0.001863
100	0.90	9.15	0.020	0.02404	0.01012	0.001789
110	0.80	9.25	0.010	0.02249	0.01046	0.001667
120	0.70	9.35	0.010	0.02220	0.01108	0.001572
130	0.60	9.45	0.010	0.02165	0.01206	0.001506
140	0.50	9.55	0.010	0.02143	0.01358	0.001460

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TABLE V

$$\text{H}_2\text{C}(\text{COOH})_2 = 0.05M. \quad \text{KMnO}_4 = 0.002M. \quad \text{Temp.} = 20^\circ.$$

Time (t).	a-z.	z.	k ₀ .	k ₁ .	k ₂ .	k _{auto} .
0 min.	10.05 ml	..	..	..	..	..
30	10.00	0.05 ml	0.001	0.00016	0.000010	0.0000729
60	9.85	0.20	0.005	0.00033	0.000033	0.0000958
90	9.40	0.65	0.015	0.00074	0.000078	0.0003365
105	9.00	1.05	0.028	0.00105	0.000105	0.0004305
120	8.40	1.65	0.040	0.00140	0.000162	0.0005816
135	7.50	2.55	0.080	0.00216	0.000250	0.0005711
150	6.15	3.90	0.090	0.00327	0.000420	0.0007907
160	4.95	5.10	0.220	0.00442	0.000640	0.0008299
170	3.50	6.55	0.145	0.00620	0.001095	0.0008290
180	1.90	8.15	0.180	0.00925	0.002371	0.0007949
190	1.40	8.65	0.050	0.01039	0.002236	0.0008252
210	1.00	9.05	0.020	0.01099	0.004288	0.0008196

TABLE VI

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_2\text{COOH} \\ | \\ \text{CH}_2\text{COOH} \end{array} = 0.05M. \quad \text{KMnO}_4 = 0.002M. \quad \text{Temp.} = 30^\circ.$$

t (hr.)	..	0	1	3	5	8	21	24
a-z(ml)	..	10.1	10.10	10.05	10.05	10.05	9.70	9.60
z(ml)	..	..	..	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.40	0.50

DISCUSSION

Since malonic and succinic acids are dibasic, it follows that there are two stages of their dissociation and the addition of $-\text{CH}_2$ group or groups also affects the reducing power of these dibasic organic acids. Our observations (vide Tables I, V, and VI and Fig. 1) show the comparative behaviour of oxalic, malonic, and succinic acids towards KMnO_4 .

Curves 2_b and 2_d (Fig. 2) show that the reduction by malonic acid is considerably affected by temperature. At 30° the reaction is much faster than at 20° . The rates of reduction by oxalic acid is very much higher than that by malonic acid (curves 1_a and 1_b) and that of succinic acid is much lower than malonic acid (Tables III and VI). In the case of succinic acid, the rate is so slow that very slight reduction of KMnO_4 is observed even after 24 hours.

Tables II-IV and Fig. 2 show that the time required to reduce a definite quantity of KMnO_4 increases as the concentration of malonic acid is decreased.

The $x-t$ curves are typically S-shaped for these acids, showing that the reaction is autocatalytic; our observations are in agreement with the mechanism suggested by

Skrabal¹ and Launer². Since the dissociation of these dibasic acids takes place in two stages, it is evident that the reaction will be fast or slow according to the H^+ -ion concentration obtained by the dissociation of these acids. The dissociation constants of these acids are in the order: oxalic acid > malonic acid > succinic acid.

FIG. 1. Comparative study of the reduction of $KMnO_4$ by oxalic and malonic acids.

$KMnO_4 = 0.002M$. Organic acid = $0.05M$. Temp. = 20° .

(1a) $KMnO_4$ —oxalic acid system.

(1b) $KMnO_4$ —malonic acid system.

According to the mechanism suggested, the reduction of Mn^{3+} ions to Mn^{2+} ions, which act as a catalyst, depends on the available concentration of $C_2O_4^{2-}$ and COO^- radicals. The autocatalytic $x-t$ curves clearly suggest that the release of $C_2O_4^{2-}$ and COO^- radicals is much less in the case of malonic and succinic acids according to the values of their dissociation constants. These curves further show that introduction of $-CH_2$ groups reduces the reducing power of these acids. The rate constants recorded in Tables I-V show that the values are not uniformly constant but gradually increase to a certain limit with time, thus supporting the role of increase of Mn^{2+} ions according to the mechanism suggested. The constancy of the rate constants is not observed except at the last stage of the reaction by using zero, uni, and bimolecular formulas. Incidentally, the rate constants derived by using the formulas for autocatalytic reaction is, by far, more satisfactory than k_p , k_t , and k_2 . Tables I-V show that the values of k_{auto} are constant in the intermediate period of the reaction. The values of the rate constants also determine the period of induction as evidenced by the very low values of k_p , k_t , k_2 , and k_{auto} in the initial stages of the reaction. These observations lend a strong support

to the mechanism suggested to explain the nature of the reaction between KMnO_4 and carboxylic acids. Further work is in progress.

FIG. 2 Influence of the conc. of malonic acid and temp. on the rate of reduction of KMnO_4 .
 $\text{KMnO}_4 = 0.002M$.

- (2_a) With 0.06M malonic acid at 30°.
 (2_b) With 0.05M malonic acid at 30°.
 (2_c) With 0.04M malonic acid at 30°.
 (2_d) With 0.05M malonic acid at 20°.

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